

Isoquinoline Alkaloids from *Fumaria indica*

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Fumaria indica (Haussk), Pulgley (fumariaceae) is referred to as *shahtera lparpata* in the Indian system of medicine¹. Previous work on the plant led to the isolation of several isoquinoline alkaloids², sterols and alkanooctacosanol derivatives³. The present study reports the isolation of a new isoquinoline glycoside and pseudo-protopine alkaloid from *F. indica*.

Results and Discussion

The uv spectrum of 1 indicated that the compound contained an isoquinoline moiety⁴. The *N*-methyl group is oriented within the shielding zone of the carbonyl group and its singlet appear at δ 1.80. The benzylic methylene adjacent to nitrogen and carbonyl appeared at 3.42 and 3.75 respectively as broad singlets. Two methylene dioxy groups resonated as two singlet at δ 5.90 and 5.94 and four aromatic protons as three singlets at δ 6.65, 6.75 and 6.90. Its mass spectrum showed the molecular ion at m/z : 353 corresponding to formula $C_{20}H_{19}O_5N$ and base peak at m/z : 163, corresponding to $C_9H_7O_3$, which is not surprising since retro-Diels-Alder cleavage should facile here and other fragments at 148 ($C_9H_8O_2$) and 190 ($C_{11}H_{12}O_2$) are in accord with the fragmentations of the isoquinoline nucleus⁵. The above data are in accord with structure 1 for pseudoprotopine⁶.

(1)

(2)

The uv-spectrum of compound 2 indicated the presence of an isoquinoline nucleus. The ir spectrum showed OH absorption at 3 450–3 400 cm^{-1} . In the 1H nmr spectrum (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6) methylene protons appeared as singlets at δ 2.91, 3.25 and 3.71 (2H each) and aromatic protons appear as three broad singlets at 6.65 (2H, s, H-1 and H-12), 6.75 (1H, s, H-4) and 7.08 (1H, s, H-9). The ^{13}C nmr showed the presence of 25 carbon atoms. Two methylenedioxy carbons appeared at 100.8 and 101.0 and C-8 appeared at 105.0 due to the attachment of glucose moiety. In the mass spectrum, the molecular ion fragment at m/z : 502.0135 corresponded to the molecular formula $C_{25}H_{28}NO_{10}$. The molecular formula taking in conjugation with the 1H nmr suggest it to be a substituted stylopin⁸. The most interesting features of the MS is the appearance of a fragment at 338 (15%) which arose due to loss of glucose moiety. The anomeric proton of glucose observed at δ 4.51 as a broad doublet (J 8 Hz) was assigned to the anomeric proton of D-glucopyranose. Compound 2 was hydrolysed with methanolic HCl and the hydrolysate worked up in the usual manner. The hydrolysate on paper chromatographic comparison with an authentic sample confirmed the sugar moiety present to be glucose. The aglycone was obtained on hydrolysis of 2 crystallised from methanol-acetone (m.p. 220°) which was further confirmed by mass spectral data. The 1H nmr spectrum of the aglycone further confirmed the structure 2 as β -D-glycopyranoside.

Experimental

The plant of *Fumaria indica* was collected from the University campus. A voucher specimen was deposited in the herbarium of the Botany Department, Faculty of Science, Jamia Hamdard, New Delhi.

The air-dried powdered herbs (1 kg) was extracted with petrol (b.p. 60–80°) and ethanol successively in a Soxhlet apparatus. The concentrate afforded brownish gummy materials (3 g). The alcohol extract was chromatographed on a column of silica gel using chloroform-methanol as eluent (95 : 5, 85–15) and afforded compounds 1 and 2 which were separated to by ptlc ($CHCl_3$: MeOH 85 : 15) and crystallised from $CHCl_3$ -MeOH (1 : 1). *Pseudoprotopine* 1; 150 mg, m.p. 198–200°, λ_{max} (MeOH) 214, 238, 291 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 678, 1 615, 1 490, 1 450, 1 440, 1 372, 1 325, 1 295, 1 260, 1 235, 1 040, 972, 800 cm^{-1} . 1H nmr δ (DMSO- d_6 , 100 MHz) 1.80 (3H, s, N- CH_3), 2.85 (2H, m, H-3, H-3'), 3.25 (2H, br s, H-2, H-2'), 3.42 (2H, s, H-1, H-1'), 3.75 (2H, s, C_6H_5 - CH_2 -N), 5.90 (2H, s, O- CH_2 -O), 5.94

(2H, s, O-CH₂-O), 6.65 (2H, s, ArH), 6.75 (1H, s, ArH), 6.90 (1H, s, ArH); ¹³C nmr δ (DMSO-d₆) 108.3 (C-1), 146.5 (C-2), 147.5 (C-3), 110 (C-4), 138.3 (C-4a), 32.0 (C-5), 58.1 (C-6), 52.0 (C-8), 117.9 (C-8a), 111.9 (C-9), 146.3 (C-10), 145.9 (C-11), 120.5 (C-12), 123.5 (C-12a), 48.1 (C-13), 180.7 (C-14), 140.5 (C-14a), 42.5 (N-CH₃), 191.0 (C₂O-CH₂-O-C₃), 100.5 (C₁₀-O-CH₂-O-C₁₁); m/z (EI, 70 eV) 353 (M⁺), C₂₀H₁₉O₅N, 323, 311, 296, 281, 267, 252, 209, 205, 190, 163, (100%), 148 (98%), 134.90, 89.76. *Psyudostylopine-8β-D-glucopyranoside* (2; 100 mg), m.p. 250°; λ_{max} (MeOH) 214, 240, 291 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 450, 3 400, 1 495, 1 470, 1 390, 1 325, 1 275, 1 245, 1 162, 1 040, 940, 910, 815 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (DMSO-d₆; 100 MHz), 2.91 (2H, s, H-5), 3.25 (2H, s, H-13'), 3.71 (2H, s, H-6, H-6'), 4.51 (1H, br d, J 8 Hz, H-8), 3.75 (2H, s, C₆H₅-CH₂-N), 5.90 (2H, s, O-CH₂-O), 6.10 (2H, s, OCH₂O) 6.65 (2H, s, H-1, H-12), 6.75 (1H, s, H-4), 6.90 (1H, s, H-9); ¹³C nmr (DMSO-d₆; 50 MHz) 105.6 (C-1), 145.1 (C-2), 146.3 (C-5), 108.4 (C-4), 127.8 (C-4a), 29.6 (C-5), 51.3 (C-6), 105.0 (C-8), 117.0 (C-8a), 106.8 (C-9), 143.3 (C-10), 146.0 (C-11), 121.0 (C-12), 128.6 (C-12a), 36.5 (C-13), 59.8 (C-14), 130.8 (C-14a), 100.8 (O-CH₂-O), 101.0 (O-CH₂-O), 102.0 (C-1'), 76.0 (C-2'), 71.20 (C-4'), 62.8 (C-6'), 78.7 (C-3', C-5'); m/z (EI, 70eV) 502.0135 (M⁺), 501 (M⁺-1), 413, 353, 338, 309, 281, 267, 209, 190, 163, 149, 148, 91, 89, 58 (100).

Compound 2 (20 mg) was dissolved in methanol (2 ml) containing concentrated HCl (2 drops) and refluxed on a water-bath for 2 h. The hydrolysate was concentrated and addition of a few drops of water yielded a white precipitate. The precipitate was filtered and the filtrate concentrated under reduced pressure to dryness. The residue was dissolved in water and spotted on Whatman's paper no. 1 alongwith authentic samples of rhamnose, galactose, fructose and glucose. The chromatogram was developed with butanol saturated with water and spots were stained with

aniline phthalate. The hydrolysed product was found identical with glucose. The solid was chromatographed over a column of Si-gel and the column was eluted with chloroform with 2% methanol. After removing the solvent, a solid was obtained which was crystallised from methanol-acetone m.p. 220°; λ_{max} (MeOH) 293, 235, 290 nm; 3 445, 1 505, 1 485, 1 460, 1 385, 1 370, 1 355, 1 215, 1 262, 1 245, 1 200, 1 185, 1 160, 1 120, 1 058, 1 042, 1 025, 1 008, 985, 970, 840, 820 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (DMSO-d₆; CDC1₃) 2.93 (2H, s, H-5), 3.30 (2H, s, H-13, H-13'), 3.85 (2H, s, H-6'), 3.80 (2H, s, C₆H₅-CH₂-N), 5.91 (2H, s, O-CH₂-O), 6.0 (2H, s, O-CH₂-O); m/z 339 (M⁺), 190, 175, 164, 146, 91, 58.

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